

PEDAGOGICAL SITUATIONS AND THEIR FEATURES

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Abstract. The article is dedicated to pedagogical situations and their characteristics in the educational process. The article examines current problems facing the modern education system, such as the effective use of scientific, technical, and advanced technology achievements in accordance with the goals, objectives, content, and methodological requirements of teaching and upbringing the younger generation.

Keywords: education and upbringing, feature, pedagogical situation, analysis, mastery, means and methods, interactivity.

Annotatsiya. Maqola ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida pedagogik vaziyatlar va ularning xususiyatlariga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada yosh avlodga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning maqsadi, vazifalari, mazmuni, uslubiy talablariga ko'ra fan, texnika va ilg'or texnologiya yutuqlaridan unumli foydalanish bugungi ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan dolzarb muammolari haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim-tarbiya, xususiyat, pedagogik vaziyat, tahlil qilish, mahorat, vosita va usullar, interfaol.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена педагогическим ситуациям и их особенностям в образовательно-воспитательном процессе. В статье рассматриваются актуальные проблемы, стоящие перед современной системой образования, такие как эффективное использование достижений науки, техники и передовых технологий в соответствии с целями, задачами, содержанием и методическими требованиями обучения и воспитания молодого поколения.

Ключевые слова: образование и воспитание, особенность, педагогическая ситуация, анализ, мастерство, средства и методы, интерактивность.

Introduction. According to the goals, objectives, content, and methodological requirements of educating the younger generation, the effective use of scientific, technical, and advanced technology achievements is one of the pressing problems facing today's education system. To increase the effectiveness of education, ensure that the individual is at the center of education, and ensure that young people acquire independent knowledge, educational institutions need well-prepared teachers who, in addition to firmly mastering knowledge in their field, are familiar with modern pedagogical technologies and interactive strategies, and know

the rules for their use in organizing educational and upbringing sessions.

Main part. The emergence of pedagogical situations in the educational process is a fact, a life story that has given rise to pedagogical issues that the teacher himself encountered in his daily life and require resolution. Some types of frequently encountered pedagogical situations allow for the rapid formulation of pedagogical tasks, their resolution, and the elimination of these situations during the analysis of cadets' actions; other types of rare situations can be complex, non-repetitive, requiring a fairly long time for resolution, and sometimes completely unsolvable.

In the course of service activities and the pedagogical process, both commanders and officer-instructors may find themselves in situations requiring prompt solutions. When we analyze the results of such situations, we either approve of our decision or, conversely, are dissatisfied with ourselves.

Solving situations arising in the educational process requires professional and pedagogical competence and experience from the teacher.

Before answering the question "What is a pedagogical situation?," it is necessary to have a brief understanding of pedagogical mastery, pedagogical activity, pedagogical etiquette, pedagogical etiquette, and the features of its manifestation.

The great educator A.S. Makarenko, emphasizing that a future educator must master the secrets of pedagogical mastery while still a cadet, says: "An educator must know how to organize, walk, joke, be cheerful, and irritable; he must behave in such a way that every action of his educates." Pedagogical activity is an activity whose content is the education, upbringing, and development of cadets.

It should be remembered that pedagogical activity is not a one-way, but a two-way collaborative activity. It involves two active parties: the teacher – the cadet – the cadet. The goal is the cadet, the cadet's personality, and its development.

Pedagogical mastery is the organization of all forms of the educational process in the most favorable and effective conditions, directing them toward the goals of personal development, forming a worldview and abilities in cadets, and awakening in them a desire for activities necessary for society.

According to Abu Ali ibn Sina, ..."a teacher should be a person with a strong character, a clear conscience, truthfulness, and a good knowledge of child-rearing methods and moral rules." The teacher must be able to penetrate the layers of the cadet's mind, studying their entire inner and outer world.

Our great poet Alisher Navoi also objectively evaluated the work of a teacher: "Even if a student becomes a king, it is worthwhile to serve the teacher," "Who taught you a single letter on the path of truth with pain."

The educator is the organizer of the educational process. The instructor is one of the sources of knowledge for cadets in providing necessary advice during lessons, during additional lessons, and at the same time during extracurricular periods.

The "Creative Teacher" may also have the same characteristics as the "Excellent Teacher." Their significant difference is that while an advanced teacher studies existing sources and carries out specific educational and upbringing work based on them, a creative teacher looks at existing sources with a critical eye. In many cases, expressing their attitude toward existing methodological guidelines, they utilize modern methodological methods that differ from existing procedures based on the requirements of conditions and situations, as well as their own capabilities.

The "innovative teacher" is distinguished by the presence of integrated pedagogical tools and methods. At the same time, innovative teachers possess the qualities of scientific analysis and the ability to look at themselves critically. Many of them are convinced that they are doing the right thing, even in the most difficult situations where others do not believe in themselves.

Educational ethics is a set of professional and moral characteristics that clarify the laws, tasks, principles, concepts, requirements, and criteria of universal and national morality in the process of education and upbringing, manifesting in the teacher's relationships with students, colleagues, parents, and heads of educational institutions. Educational etiquette is manifested primarily in the interaction between the officer-teacher and the cadets.

However, it should be noted that such an approach is a somewhat limited point of view. After all, the professional ethics of an officer-teacher are manifested not only in the process of communication with cadets but also as a primary need throughout their entire career. In other words, the concept of pedagogical etiquette refers to the life system of the officer-teacher's worldview. The content of the concept of pedagogical ethics, along with morality, includes economic, political, and legal aspects.

When forming the qualities of a teacher's ethics as a component of moral education and upbringing, it is advisable to analyze related concepts in two directions: the first is the attitude of society toward the teacher's personality; the second is the attitude of the teacher's personality toward society.

Summarizing these definitions, which do not contradict each other and complement each other in content, it can be said that the pedagogical situation is an integral part of the pedagogical process and pedagogical reality, through which the officer-teacher manages the pedagogical process and the pedagogical system. Pedagogical situations are of great importance in the activities of an officer-teacher. They encompass all the achievements and shortcomings of the pedagogical process and the pedagogical system. They play an important role in forming the experience of pedagogical activity. For this reason, every educator must have a personal archive of recorded or memorized situations. This archive is preserved and replenished throughout the teacher's career and is considered the personal wealth of the educator.

In the military-pedagogical process, in addition to the listed situations, critical situations may arise during military disciplines, for example, during practical field exercises. At such a time, intense psychological tension may require both the officer-instructor and the cadet, in addition to applying knowledge and experience, to exert a strong will and overcome fear or panic. In such situations, the correctness of the task and the rational resolution of the situation depend on the skill and professional competence of the officer-instructor.

A pedagogical situation is a repetition of the pedagogical process per unit of time. Pedagogical situations are of great importance; they encompass all the achievements and shortcomings of the pedagogical process and the pedagogical system and play an important role in shaping the experience of pedagogical activity. In military pedagogy, the educational and pedagogical situation is defined as a real situation in which a decision is made regarding methods of pedagogical influence on the serviceman.

In the military-pedagogical process, it is necessary to take into account the importance of tasks such as the nature of the relationship between the officer-instructor and the cadets, the principle of unity of command, adherence to subordination, teaching students to analyze various situations in the process of future military service, and making quick decisions. The specific nature of these relationships and the differences within them can lead to a discrepancy between the values, norms, and interests of the participants in the movement, resulting in conflicts.

The formation and development of military-pedagogical qualities and professional-pedagogical skills of an officer is a process with internal contradictions and under the influence of many factors. This process does not occur spontaneously, but is managed and depends primarily on the level of knowledge, worldview, and the level of spiritual, mental, aesthetic, and physical development of each officer. An officer-teacher is required to constantly improve their pedagogical skills, develop their professional level, and possess deep knowledge, solid skills, and qualifications in their specialty.

In conclusion, it can be said that the higher the level of professional competence of the officer-teacher in the successful course of the military-pedagogical process, the fewer unpleasant pedagogical situations arise, or even those that arise are resolved rationally and successfully.

Solving pedagogical problems expresses the essence of pedagogical activity. Both standard and creative solutions can be used when solving pedagogical problems.

Thus, pedagogical situations arising in the process of military education and ways to resolve them positively are considered one of the most pressing tasks of today.

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